

Breaking barriers to game-based learning for active ageing and healthy lifestyles

A qualitative interview study with experts in the field

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Abstract—This study aims to explore a set of design components that a game-based learning programme should have in order to encourage active ageing and healthy lifestyles. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with 10 Subject Matter Experts from the Industry and the Educational Sector in the fields of Games, Human-Computer Interaction, Psychology and Ageing Studies. A thematic analysis of the interviewee’s answers identified a set of recommendations for the following topics: Designing age-friendly environments; Perspectives on the (Co-) Design Process; Designing for learning and behaviour change; and the monetization of a game.

Keywords—*game-based learning; active ageing; healthy lifestyles; qualitative interview*

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent advances in the use of Information and Communication Technologies in the urban, mobile and home spaces have challenged the field of Interaction Design and, thus, the mental and emotional representations of player-citizens towards their environment [1]. Indeed, the parameters of Usability, Effectiveness, Satisfaction and User Experience (UX) seem to be no longer sufficient, when referring to the view of infrastructure, platforms and software presented as a service (IaaS, PaaS and SaaS). Hence, such concepts as resilience, happiness, empathy, altruism, wellbeing and quality of life have become key concepts for the design process [2].

A number of studies have been published regarding the use of emotional [3] and affective computing [4], however, they tend to focus on the transference of human emotions and affect to robotics - e.g. [5]–[8]. Very little is known about the design of applications, especially games, in such a way that they can both predict the human potential to act upon their environment and have an impact on wellbeing and quality of life.

Furthermore, researchers have shown an increased interest in *gamification* and games with a purpose – e.g. [1], [9]–[12] and, therefore, understanding game thinking and its interconnection with behaviour-related outcomes, problem-solving capacity and decision-making have been central in game studies and interaction design.

Alongside these challenges, the world population is ageing and there is an increasing need to assess the effectiveness of digitally-mediated solutions for encouraging active ageing. However, most of the solutions presented seem to focus on illness prevention and rehabilitation – e.g. [11], [13], [14], rather than also covering other relevant concepts beyond health according to the definition of active ageing provided by the World Health Organisation [15] – i.e. sense of security and participation in society.

This study used a thematic analysis of qualitative interviews with experts in the field, in order to address the following question: What are the main recommendations for designing a game-based learning programme for encouraging active ageing and healthy lifestyles?

This paper begins by discussing emotional and behavioural design and related work on game-based approaches for active ageing and healthy lifestyles. It then presents information on the procedures used for carrying out the study, the participants, ethical considerations and the instruments used for data collection and analysis. The paper concludes by outlining the identified recommendations suggested by experts in the fields of Games, Human-Computer Interaction, Psychology and Age Studies to consider, when designing digital games for active ageing and healthy lifestyles.

II. DESIGNING FOR ACTIVE AGEING AND HEALTHY LIFESTYLES

This section discusses both emotional and behavioural design of game-based approaches for active ageing and healthy lifestyles.

A. Emotional and behavioural design

There has been a growing interest in studying the role of emotions and behaviours for developing technologies that have an impact on the end-users' wellbeing and quality of life [2], [16].

Along with recent developments in Artificial Intelligence and Sentimental Computing Analysis, such market solutions as Amazon Alexa and First Home Olly are examples that show the potential of the system to recognize emotions, be aware of the users' context and react accordingly [17].

If, traditionally, end-users were seen as merely as cognitive and physical processors and there was a dualism between machines and humans, nowadays emotional aspects, different types of pleasures and the psychological wellbeing of the end users have become central to interface design [18].

According to Jordan [18], such dehumanising perspective on the role of the end-users as a physical and cognitive processor that overlooked their emotions has evolved to the use of a Human-Factor specialist in order to mediate the interaction of the users with interface design. In fact, the user-friendly computer Apple was a big step towards introducing

direct command lines for executing, metaphors and icons and in that way, levelling up the concerns of HCI specialists from functionality to usability and pleasure.

The same author [18] also draws our attention to the fact that there are four types of pleasures that can be associated to a product (either technology-mediated or not). These types of pleasures are [18]:

- *Physio-pleasure*: This type of pleasure can be sensed through the use of visual (e.g. animations, graphics...), auditory (speech, sounds, frequency), olfactory (smell declines), gustatory (flavours) or somatic perception (tactile – touch, haptic – temperature, pressure or pain, *kinesthetic* – motion, force, body, limb movement). These pleasures are often derived from physical environment and body personalization;
- *Socio-pleasure*: This type of pleasure stems from social identity (codes and conventions, status) and relationships with others;
- *Psycho-pleasure*: This type of pleasure often derives from cognitive-emotional reactions (e.g. moods, self-confidence, dreams, aspirations...); and
- *Ideo-pleasure*: This type of pleasure often derives from personal ideologies and the view of products as an art form.

Similarly, the author Norman [3] reports that there are three levels in which design can have an impact on the end-user's emotions: (a) visceral that is based on the product's appearance and relies on rapid judgments and human's senses; (b) behavioural that refers to the pleasure and experience of use; and (c) reflective that acts at a conscious level and is being expressed through self-image, personal satisfaction and memories.

In regards to the behavioural change, there are a number of theories – e.g. health belief model, transtheoretical model, relapse prevention, information processing, social cognitive theory, theory of reasoned actions, social support, community organization model, ecological models, organizational change and diffusion model [19], [20], [21] that can have implications for designing learning environments [22]. These implications can be [22]: (a) Simulate scenarios in which the

seriousness of the problem is presented and inform about the change benefits; (b) Enable scaffolding; (c) Reward goal achievements; (d) Provide alternative coping strategies; (e) Associate different types of cues to actions and daily habits/routines; (f) Provide easy-to-remember information; (g) Link the information with previous knowledge/past experiences; (h) Remind “small wins”; (i) Promote social accountability; (j) Enable social modelling; (k) Build a trust network and a social status; (l) Inform about policies/initiatives; and (m) Provide context-aware to changes in behaviours.

In the same vein, Calvo and Peters [2] note that technology can have an impact on human potential and wellbeing by fostering positive emotions and allocating ‘remembering experiences’; encouraging autonomy, competence and self-actualization; creating self-awareness and self-compassion through metacognition, experimental cognition, affect and behaviour; investing in mindfulness interventions; and, finally, reinforcing empathy, compassion and altruism through storytelling, role-play and communal goals.

In view of all that was mentioned so far, one may assume that emotional and behavioural design has become of utmost importance for bringing a much more humanistic approach to the Human-Computer Interaction field.

B. Game-based approaches for active ageing and healthy lifestyles

Over the past few years, a considerable amount of literature has been published on the use of games for active ageing and intergenerational relationships [23, 24]. Indeed, these studies - e.g. [25]-[33] have found that games can be beneficial to active ageing by: (a) Improving cognitive functioning [25]; (b) Training learners’ memory and encouraging social interactions [26]-[30]; (c) Challenging the thinking process and exercising hand-eye coordination; and (d) Positively influencing the learners’ self-concept, self-esteem and quality of life [29], [31]-[33].

In terms of game preferences and skills that gamers over 50 would like to practice, a survey [34] with 245 gamers has revealed that adventure games with problem-solving, strategy and memory games were preferred, whereas problem-solving, spatial

and temporal memory skills as well as calculation were the most cited skills.

Although there are some attempts that were made by the Industry to meet the needs of this target group, e.g. Nintendo Brain Age, most of the solutions presented did not involve the participants in the design process of digital games or covered the different variables of active ageing (health, sense of security and participation in society) [23]. Furthermore, a number of recommendations [23], [35] were proposed in order to address digital games for the older population, such as:

- Designing game elements that are similar to real-world scenarios;
- Fostering collaboration among players and reinforcing communication networks;
- Developing digital games with a purpose;
- Taking into account the cost of the equipment or the players’ physical limitations;
- Reinforcing the use of immediate rewards;
- Prioritizing *player versus environment* challenges over *player versus player* scenarios;

In the context of behavioural design and games, game-based psychotherapy [36] is suggested to enable players to express their beliefs, thoughts and experiences through game-playing, with the purpose of improving their lifestyles, wellbeing and quality of life. Specifically, games with a purpose of encouraging habits and adherence to new behaviours should: (a) assess the intrinsic motivations of the target group; (b) design quests that can be accomplished both in the digital and physical world; (c) reward the player with experience and social points in order to show progress and use a community as a ‘call to actions’; (d) integrate avatars as they can strengthen the sense of empathy between the player and the avatar, who has a purpose, a mission, and a change in his/her habits; and (e) encourage the collection of meaningful objects as they can be associated to the effort made by the player.

Together, these studies indicate that there are many recommendations for addressing active ageing and behavioural design. However, much uncertainty

still exists regarding experts' perspectives in the field regarding game-based learning for active ageing and healthy lifestyles.

III. METHOD

According to Glaser and Strauss [37], many of the challenges in social research can be met through the use of Grounded Theory. Indeed, when delving into such changeable phenomena as trends in the game market and design for health and active ageing, a theory grounded in data obtained *in situ* and at the moment rather than relying on predetermined information seems to be the most suitable practice. Hence, the inductive approach used in Grounded Theory was applied to this study in order to conduct a set of semi-structured interviews with Subject Matter experts in the fields of Games, Human-Computer Interaction, Psychology and/or Ageing Studies.

A. Participants and sampling

A convenience sampling (n=10) of experts in the field of Games, Human-Computer Interaction, Psychology, Marketing and Ageing Studies was used. The inclusion criteria were: voluntary participation, and being familiar with at least one of the following topics: (a) games; (b) learning and changes in behaviour and; (c) age-friendly environments. The rationale for including these interviewee's profiles as criteria was the following:

- Acquire their perspective on the use of games in learning and changes in behaviours; and
- Understand the role of digitally-mediated approaches to meet the challenges of the ageing process.

A number of possible interviewees were then contacted and out of the 52 invitations, 10 interviewees agreed to take part in the study. In total, there were 10 acceptances, 2 refusals and 40 no answers.

Out of the 10 interviewees, 8 were male and 2 female. Six (6) of the interviewees were researchers whereas three (3) were practitioners in the game industry and one (1) was both a researcher and practitioner in the game industry.

General information about the interviewees is shown in Table I.

TABLE I. PARTICIPANTS' GENERAL INFORMATION

ID	Context	Description
1	Educational Sector	Researcher in User Experience and Information Architecture. Professor in Computer Science with a vast experience in joint education-industry projects (e.g. <i>Microsoft, Nokia</i>)
2	Both	Freelance game designer, consultant and lecturer. Experience in game development and previous involvement in such game projects as the ones carried out by Bullfrog Productions or Madden NFL Football.
3	Industry	Vast experience in the game industry and consultant in monetisation, videogames and <i>gamification</i> . Relevant game projects: Smashy City, Batman and The Flash: Hero Run, Jelly Jiggle and Farm All Day.
4	Academy	Research Associate at the Disruptive Media Learning Lab. Background in Psychology with the following research interests: identities in online communities, learning practices and games.
5	Industry	Vast experience in the tabletop games industry and involvement in various game projects (i.e. triple A console MMOs and free-to-play games).
6	Industry	Vast experience in game design. Relevant game projects included SEGA Rally Revo and Colin McRae: DiRT Rally.
7	Educational Sector	Professor and Researcher with expertise in 'silver gaming' and the use of old and new media by older adults.
8	Educational Sector	Research fellow for the Behaviour and interventions Research Group (Coventry University) and Public Health Warwickshire with the following research interests: evidence informed making, social marketing, health behaviour change and eHealth.
9	Educational Sector	Researcher in Educational Technology and Learning Design at Simon Fraser University with a focus on ageing and technology. Research interests: digital games and digital storytelling with older adults and intergenerational relationships.
10	Educational Sector	Senior lecturer and researcher with background in Artificial Intelligence, in-game learning, computer games development and digital media. Research interests: virtual reality an applications for learning and training.

IV. DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

Audio recorded semi-structured individual interviews were held between July 2017 and October 2017 and lasted approximately 60 min each. Ten interviews were conducted (either face-to-face, over the telephone or by e-mail), audiotaped and transcribed. The face-to-face interviews took place at Coventry University and a convenient time was arranged for both the interviewee and the interviewer.

A protocol for conducting the interviews and analysing the data was followed. This protocol was divided into the following steps: 1. Introduction/Instructions and Standards Procedures; 2. Ice-breaker questions; 3. Four/five questions; and

4. Thank-you statement. Table II provides an overview of the questions used to interview Subject Matter Experts in the fields of Games/Human-Computer Interaction, whereas Table III presents the questions posed to the Subject Matter Experts in Psychology, Marketing or Ageing Studies.

TABLE II. OVERVIEW OF QUESTIONS USED TO INTERVIEW SUBJECT MATTER EXPERTS IN THE FIELDS OF GAMES/HUMAN-COMPUTER INTERACTION

<i>Data Collection Questions</i>	<i>Data Analysis Questions</i>
1. How can we attract the player's attention to the information transmitted and changes in behaviour through a game-based approach? / How do you see <i>gamification</i> in the context of learning and changes in behaviours?	What are the main factors that can foster learning and changes in behaviour?
2. In your opinion, what could be a pervasive game scenario for motivating acting ageing and healthy lifestyles?	
3. Do you see <i>gamification</i> as a players' mind-set solution or a game designer's product? Why?	What's the role of game designers in <i>gamification</i> ? / What's the role of players' mind-set in <i>gamification</i> ?
4. Can a gamified system work by extending actions that occur in the physical space to the digital one? What is your view on that?	
5. How can games generate a culture of care and prevention outside of the medical system?	What are the main factors that can generate a culture of care and prevention outside of the medical system?
6. In your perspective, what role can informational literacy perform in order to overcome the commercial war that can occur between changing or manipulating behaviours?	What are the main strategies that can be adopted in order to avoid manipulation of behaviours in <i>gamification</i> ?
7. What are the main misconceptions or drawbacks of these game-based approaches that game designers should take into account?	What are the drawbacks/challenges of the game-based approaches for learning and changes in behaviours?
8. What are the opportunities for <i>gamification</i> and serious games?	What are the opportunities for <i>gamification</i> and serious games?
9. In your opinion, what the future holds for serious games and <i>gamification</i> ?	

The verbatim transcripts were analysed using qualitative content analysis. The transcriptions were reread and coded using NVivo 11 and the patterns of the interviewee's statements were identified and highlighted. The codes used were: Recommendations for designing age-friendly environments; Perspectives on the (Co-) Design Process; Designing for learning and behaviour change; and The monetization process of a game.

TABLE III. OVERVIEW OF QUESTIONS USED TO INTERVIEW SUBJECT MATTER EXPERTS IN THE FIELDS OF PSYCHOLOGY AND AGEING STUDIES

<i>Data Collection Questions</i>	<i>Data Analysis Questions</i>
1. What drives Human behaviours?	What are the main factors that can foster learning and changes in behaviour?
3. In your opinion, can technologies trigger changes in behaviour? If so, in what way?	What are the key technological features that can influence changes in behaviours?
3. How can we transform Human behaviours into daily routines?	What are the main factors that lead Human behaviours into habits/routines?
4. In your opinion, how can we create environments that are better places for encouraging active ageing?	What are the main features of an age-friendly environment?
5. In your perspective, what could the technology industry do to contribute to age-friendly contexts?	What are the opportunities for age-friendly technologies?
6. What challenges do you foresee in the new approaches to create age-friendly environments?	What are the challenges for age-friendly technologies?

A. Ethical considerations

The interviewees gave their consent regarding the way the information would be used and the right to stop or withdraw from the research at any time. By signing that form, the participants agreed with the following: (a) The interview would be recorded and a transcript produced; (b) direct quotations or a summary interview would be anonymised; (c) The recording would be destroyed after 5 years; (d) The participants would voluntarily take part in the project and have the right to stop and withdraw at any time; and (f) The right to ask any questions the participants could have.

V. RESULTS

This section gives a brief overview of the interviewee's perspectives on the main recommendations for designing age-friendly environments and the (co-) design process.

A. Recommendations for designing age-friendly environments

When surveyed regarding the recommendations for designing age-friendly environments, the interviewees outlined the fact that these environments should: (a) foster social connectedness and demystify ageing bias, (b) take into account different age-cohorts when addressing products to this target group; (c) not focus on age-related difficulties or illness prevention; (d) train skills through cognitive challenges and foster life-long

learning, establishing a strong link with everyday life; and (e) make the participants familiar with the interfaces. The following quotations illustrate these concerns:

"[...] increasing social connectedness, reducing ageism and contributing to life-long learning. These aspects are very important to encourage active ageing [...] The other is not only focus on the disease or age-related difficulties, but to make designs that also focus on the positive aspects of ageing [...] risk of seeing older adults as their age-related difficulties, and having approaches only focus on reducing this, or increasing that. It is important that the person is respected as something beyond their age-related conditions." - Interviewee 9

"If you take somebody They understand TV, they understand the computer with Internet connection and they might be coerced to interact with a fitness band. Anything else, I think that it will be a struggle [...]" - Interviewee 1

"I think that we should really try to involve them because I think that older people is a diverse group including women, men, younger-old, old-old, higher educated and non-higher educated [...] Connect to their everyday life." - Interviewee 7

B. Perspectives on the (Co-)Design Process

The interviewees argue that there is a general lack of co-design practices in both the Industry and the Educational Sector. According to their comments, end-users are often involved during gameplay testing but not during the early stages of the design process, which can sometimes lead to a failure of thinking about the representative player. Furthermore, the interviewees highlight the importance of low-fidelity prototypes for getting the players into game thinking and obtaining their feedback. These are some of their quotations:

"If you get a prototype, something that works, get them [the users] on it, iterate and obtain their feedback. Check whether the motivation of the target group and those ideas do not compromise the whole idea of the game" - Interviewee 3

"Normally we don't really focus on test design. We can't ask all the players because we're hoping to have millions of them, right? We can try a design and we can make a prototype and we very often do that and then we invite people to play the prototype and you refine the prototype based on their feedback and so we involve them in the very early in the design stage – after the concept but before the mechanics to prototype different ideas about how to play and what feels like and so they come in and sit down and play [...]" The approach you might vote is to imagine the

representative player [‘Who is the person you're really trying to reach?’ and put yourself in their shoes and become your representative players and think yourself - Will my player enjoy doing this?]" - Interviewee 2

C. Design for learning and behaviour change

When designing for learning and behaviour change, the interviewees made the following recommendations: (a) reinforce the presence of the player in the environment; (b) stimulate the players' subconscious by overweighting internal motivation (i.e. skills, beliefs, self-efficacy) and external elements that leads to human behaviours; (c) use social elements, scenario building and changes in the game plot; (d) interlink between cognitive and affective dimensions; (e) strengthen the dialogue between both game-design and the subject area; and (f) establish a link between games and outdoor activities and rely heavily on notifications. Nevertheless, the interviewees highlighted two main problems with game-like activities for shaping behaviour – i.e., both manipulation of behaviours and too much focus on PBLs (Points, Badges and Leaderboards), in which information literacy can have an important role. For example, these are some of the interviewee's quotations:

"Technologies can most definitely trigger changes in our behaviours at both the conscious and unconscious levels. For example, simple reminders on our phones can be helpful for medication adherence levels. For example, simple reminders on our phones can be helpful for medication adherence behaviour. Technologies can also target our unconscious processes by releasing smells to trigger certain behaviours like eating." - Interviewee 8

"[...] a cognitive dimension and an emotional/affective dimension. I think that these two need to be interconnected but then need to think about the information from the start and the relational, emotional things are also important. It is a point I'd recommend that we look at when talking about behaviours – not only the cognitive dimension but also the affective one" - Interviewee 7

"I see some problems with using games and gamification to shape behaviour, of course – there is a huge ethical discussion even when using it for a good reason [...] All the techniques that we developed that can shape behaviour could be caught by the army, advertisement or insurance. What I see in many gamification and serious games applications is a very behaviourist approach to human motivation, so you do something – you get a reward – you do something – you get a reward – you do something - you get a reward, which I think it can work in a short-term but I don't think it can go very far – you can't change behaviours

in short-term but you can change mind-sets.”- Interviewee 4

“Information literacy can assist in the changing of behaviour as it encourages people to identify the need for information, locate it, evaluate it, and apply it to assist in changing of behaviour. The information being sort has a role to play on the effectiveness of informational literacy. For example, health information can be activity pursued or avoided in order to delay the acquisition of the information. The pursuit of information in the case of health may depend on a variety of factors, such as an individual’s traits and confidence”- Interviewee 10

D. The monetization process of a game

Opinions differed related to the monetisation strategy adopted in a game: (a) free-to-play or (b) giving a faithful price and adding extra hidden packages. These are some of the interviewee’s perspectives:

“[...] That method ‘free to play’ is retaining your customers, you need them playing for a certain amount of time [...]”- Interviewee 3

“The issue with free-to-play model is to have to stop it [the game] with something that is bored [...]. More and more big titles like Destiny are giving players a faithful price of the game, adding two or three expansion packages [...] – visual UI items that you’d not be able to achieve through normal game-playing, which allows your character to stand out from the crowd. Monetization choice is about get money to achieve – this is more getting money to stand out from the crowd” - Interviewee 6

VI. CONCLUSION

The aim of this study was to explore the main design components that a game-based learning strategy needs for encouraging active ageing and healthy lifestyles. Semi-structured interviews conducted with 10 Subject Matter Experts from the Industry and the Education Sector revealed the following requirements for developing game-based learning for active ageing:

- Take into account different age-cohorts, when addressing products to this target group;
- Do not focus on age-related difficulties or illness prevention;
- Train skills through cognitive challenges, foster life-long learning, and establish a strong link with everyday life;

- Familiarise the participants with the interface;
- Introduce players into game thinking and feedback during the early stages of the game but be prepared to manage the whole process and to make final decisions;
- Reinforce the presence of the player in the player environment;
- Stimulate the players’ subconscious by overweighting internal motivations (i.e. skills, beliefs, self-efficacy) and external elements that lead to human behaviours;
- Introduce social elements, scenario building and changes into the game plot;
- Establish an interlink between cognitive and affective dimensions;
- Strengthen the dialogue between game design and the subject area;
- Establish a link between games and outdoor activities and rely heavily on notifications; and
- Monetize the game for standing out from the crowd instead of associating it to the general game achievement.

To sum up, these findings extend our knowledge of current recommendations drawn from the literature review for developing game-based learning for active ageing. A limitation of this study is that a convenience sample was used, so attempts to generalize beyond these interviewees are not warranted and results should be interpreted with caution. Future work is necessary with a larger number of interviewees from the International Industry and Education Sector.

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